

Non-Predefined Life Signs Detection for Disaster Survivors Rescue

Mbaitiga Zacharie¹, Tanaka Shosaku²

National Institute of Technology, Okinawa
College, Department of Media Information
Engineering, Japan¹

Ritsumeikan University,
Department of Literature, Japan²

Abstract: No one can tell or predict when and where a natural disaster such as an earthquake or tornado will occur and the damages they may cause. Or an overflow of a large amount of water beyond its normal limit (water flood) shallowing city as we used to watch on news TV after the passage of a strong typhoon causing heavy rain. These natural disasters occur every day and anywhere around the globe are not new. And we cannot not prevent them from occurring in spite of the best technology we have in our possession now. But saving lives after their occurring is still possible and the best technology for this is the combination of AUV and the image processing. Image processing is one of the best ever invented technology by human since the course on technology development between scientists for sustainable development of our society. In order word “image processing is the technology that meets the needs of the 21st society we live in without compromising the ability of future generation to meet what they need to make the use of this technology efficiency. This paper proposes non-predefined life signs detection for disaster survivors rescue when a disaster occur and especially during a floodwater. In this research we use the matrix-based pairs of opposing pixels positioned directly around the observed point that belongs to the edge of the life signs target. At first one-dimension matrix for bitmap memorization values of the RGB components of pixel is used. Next these values of the RGB components of pixel color are copied from bitmap to matrix. The number of bytes in a row is rounded up to the nearest number divisible by four. As a result, the method clearly detects all life signs edge made by human using any type of item around them with 95%.

Keywords: Life signs; Image processing; Disaster; Edge detection; Rescue

I. INTRODUCTION

We human beings are intensely virtual creatures. Most of the information we acquire comes through our eyes and the related circuitry in our brains, rather than through touch, smell, hearing or taste. Far better or worse, that is also the way scientists acquire information from their experiments. But the skills in interpreting image developed by millions of year's evolution do not deal as well with scientific images as they do with real world experiences. Understanding the difference in the types of information to be extracted, and the biases introduced by our vision system is a necessary requirement for the scientists who would trust his or her results. The percentage of environmental information that flows through visual pathway has been estimated at

90% to 95% for a typical human without any sensory impairment. Indeed, our dependence on vision can be judge from the availability of corrective means, raging from eye glasses to laser eye surgery.

Compare to human beings, not all animals depend on or use their sight to extend that we do. Following are some examples of how animals get information in their surroundings. Bats and dolphins use echolocation on sonar to probe the world around them. Pit vipers send infrared radiation. Moles living underground trade sight for sensitive touch organs around their nose. Bloodhound's follows scents and butterflies have taste organs so sensitive they can detect single molecules. Some eels generate and sense electric fields to interact with their surroundings. Fish and alligators have pressure sensors that detect very sight motions in their

Corresponding Author: Mbaitiga Zacharie. Dept. of Media Information Engineering, National Institute of Technology, Okinawa College. 905 henoko, Okinawa, Japan. Tel: +81-98-055-4174, Fax: +81-980-55-4012, E-mail: zacharie@okinawa-ct.ac.jp

watery environment. Birds and bees both have the ability to detect the polarization of light as an aid to location sun's position on a cloud day. Birds and some bacteria seem to be able to sense the orientation of Earth's magnetic field, another aid to navigation [8].

It is not easy for human to imagine what the world looks like to a bat, eel, or mole. Indeed, even the world imagines demonstrated the problem. The root word imagine implies pictures. When the time goes on and the necessity of the image is sensed by human beings due to its role in our daily life. Different types of processing pictures and the way to use them become more and more interesting. So, we start processing image in the way we like in different method on each domain by taking the advantages of the on growing technologies. Scientists and researchers have devoted many efforts in the image treatment for different purposes including skin color detection [9]. Where the skin color can provide a useful and robust cue for human-related image analysis, such as face detection, pornographic image filtering and moving object tracking as well as people retrieval in the datasets and internet. On the top of all image processing system Edge detection is one of the most important areas of the image processing that many researches have been done on it. The edge is a characterized by its height, slope, angle and horizontal coordinate of the slope mid-point. An edge exists if the edge height is greater than a specific value and an ideal edge detector should produce and edge information localized to a single pixel located at the mid-point of the slope [10]. Tracking by Detection is also reported in the open literature which brings us to an image processing method and deflection method fully from the edge detection. Here it is. When we assume that we will see only one object in each of video that the state we wish to track is position in the image, and that we can build a reliable detector for the object we wish to track or to detect. In this case tracking is straightforward: we report the location of the detector response in each frame of the video. This observation is a good source of simple and effective tracking strategies, because we can build good detectors for some objections recognition. For example, consider tracking a red ball on a green background of an image where the detector might simply look for a red pixel to mention only a few cognition strategies among thousand methods in the image processing domain. In this paper we propose a Non-Predefined Life Signs Detection for Disaster Survivors Rescue. Robert's gradient operator which consists of 2×2 matrix is used to compute the gradient of the image at every point in the image by evaluating the correlation

of the image. Once the computation of the gradient is completed, we then combine these gradients to obtain the gradient vector magnitude for the target signs contour detection.

II. RELATED WORKS

Many research has been done and are still going on, on the image processing recognition system for the sustainable development of our society for better life style. Following are some selected previous works.

In [1] the author has proposed Edge Detection and Curvature Calculation in the visual System on finding the negative peaks in the visual system. They applied two kinds of ganglion cell on center cells and off-center cells with the following's assumptions. First the size of the excitation region of the receptive field is decided from the spatial frequency which shows the spatial characteristics of the filter in the human retina. Second the center of the receptive filed is not fixed but changes according to an input image. These methods used was based on the previous works of [2-3].

Tracking and recognition of moving object in a monocular Image Sequence based on Visual Characteristics has been proposed by [4]. Their method uses a mouse-like function for estimating hand shape from input with a monocular camera, with which a computer user feels no restraint or awkwardness. To realize mouse-like function, the system must distinguish between pointing the left and right mouse buttons. Together with the hand shape used as the enter key, the system must be able to recognize at least four classes. This, they involve conversion of sequential image from Cartesian coordinates to log-polar coordinates. Temporal and spatial subtractions and color information are used to extract the hand region. The original of log-polar coordinates is chosen as the center of the acquired image, but once the hand has been extracted, the estimated centroid position of the hand region in the next frame obtained from current hand position and speed is used as the origin to convert. Next, recognition of the hand shape is carried out by competitive approach.

Fish Recognition Based on features extraction from Size and Shape Measurements using Neural-Network is proposed in [5]. Their recognition process focuses on the isolation a pattern of interest in the image containing pattern of fish, then the image features extraction is performed by relying on the size and the shape measurements. For the size and shape measurements they use the distance and angle measurements to calculate the features extracted from the fish. The

distance measurement is the length of twelve landmarks point in the fish while the angle measurements are the angle between the landmark points. After that they trained the fish data set with Neural Network termination 0.01 in 4.1.1 epochs the value of learning constant rate. Three hidden layers have been used to activate their goal.

Method of Object detection for Mobile Robot is described in [7]. The purpose of the proposed object recognition system is to detect object in the robot path for collision during its navigation. This collision avoidance system is done by two steps of image generations and verification which involve the Gabor features extraction classification. A Novel edge detector for Color Image Based on Multi-Criteria Decision Making with Evidential Reasoning is proposed in [11]. The authors divide color image into three channels before using the traditional gray image edge detectors to obtain the edge in each channel. Where the final edge images are obtained through a fusion step according to a chosen rule. To address discordant results of the edge detection in the three channels and uncertainty when combining results with COWA-ER and FCWA-ER approaches have been introduced. These two methods have been extracted from the previous work such as COWA [12] and FCOWA [13] respectively to solve the MCDM issues.

III. METHOD

When talking about image processing recognition system, the first thing we need to keep in mind is that the ideal object recognition system would have several properties. It should recognize many different objects. This is much more difficult than its sounds. To recognize very number of objects we need to know how to organize them in to data structure that is easily searched given image data. In particular we need to know what measurement can be used to distinguish between objects as opposed to distinguishing instance [14]. Following are some requirements for ideal recognition system.

- *An ideal recognition system would recognize objects seen against many different backgrounds.* This appears to be very difficult. Ideally an appropriate object representation would help organizing the image into segments that might have come from object category without reference to a particular instance and those that could not.
- *An Ideal recognition system would recognize objects as an appropriate level of abstraction.* Example human can tell a chair is a chair even if they have not seen that particular chair before.

They do not even need to have seen that model of chair before.

- *An ideal recognition system would made useful inferences about the special properties of particular instances.* Example Assume that all chairs are instances of a single category (it is by no means obvious this is true). It would not be particularly helpful to simply name every chair a chair. We may need to know something about special properties of this instance to sit in it. Is it large enough? Does it have paddle seat? Does it have arms?
- *An Ideal recognition system would produce useful responses to unfamiliar objects.* Humans often encounter object that are at least in detail unfamiliar and can usually cope with this unfamiliarity. Few people can name most species of animal for example but most can tell whether an animal they cannot name is furry, is asleep and so on. The computer vision system or recognition design for a particular purpose will by all mean encounter unfamiliar objects regularly and they cannot simply be ignored. It should give positive feedback to the system designers which is not always the case.
- *An Ideal recognition system that helps achieve goals.* How we categorize an object that we see might reasonably depend on what that we want to do. For example, if we wish to sit a large, flat rock might be a seat. This is not always true of al rocks, so this collection of possible uses cannot be obtained by inheritance.
- *An Ideal recognition system would produce responses of useful complexity.* An object recognition system that named every object in an image might be very difficult to use because most image have many objects, most of which are not interesting. A picture of a room might well have a chair in it, a floor and some cushions.

Current recognition strategies typically perform rather poorly when measured against requirements. This is not because they are not bad. The problem is just very difficult. The dominant current object recognition strategy involves attaching a plausible set of features to a multiclass classifier, and then training the classifier with a set of examples for each class. All such recognition can be described rather broadly as template matchers; where the template and the matching cost are implicit in the classifier [14]. Our algorithm is based on

the assumption that the edge contour of the object at the image is noticeable somehow with the neck eye if there is a significant difference between the colors of the pairs of opposing pixels positioned directly around the observed point that belongs to the edge of the life sign target. We refer this method to the pairs of points which can form the straight line that passes through the observed point. Following is the sample point we have use in the development of this system.

Observed point: 000 010 100 001
Pairs of opposing point.:121 020 020 020.

Basically, this mean that we must find the maximum value of color differences for four pairs of opposing points and if the value is different from the predefined. When this is confirmed, we assign a different value for the color to the observed point. So that the resulting picture becomes edged point. Following are the processing contour detection step by step.

- Step 1: We started by locking bitmap inside the memory for faster processing before the bitmap data is loaded. The load address of the first byte of the bitmap is pointer to the address
- Step 2: We declare the matrix data which should contain all bytes of the bitmap. The bitmap must contain 24 bytes per pixel. One byte for each component of the RGB color pixels. Because of the way the bitmap data are stored in the memory, we rounded up number of bytes in the row to the nearest number divisible by four. So, that one row of the bitmap can always contain the same or larger number of bytes that is necessary for memorizing data for actual number of points in the row.
- Step 3: Declare one dimension matrix for bitmap memorization values of the RGB components of pixel.
- Step 4: Copy the values of the RGB components of pixel color from bitmap to matrix.
- Step 5: We declare the second matrix data to form 2x2 matrix. Then copy the bitmap value of the RGB component of color pixel from one dimensional to two-dimensional matrix and fill the matrix brightness with the values of the brightness of pixel. At this stage we were ready to load the bitmap, when we loaded the bitmap, all RGB values

components color pixel returned in opposite direction from RGB to BGR.

- Step 6: Finally, we copied the new value of the RGB component of the pixel color from matrix back to the bitmap.
- Step 7: Once this process is completed, we the unlocked bitmap inside the memory and show the processing image.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To validate the new proposed Life Signs detection for human survivor rescue during the disaster, we have chosen the items that can be found at home at any time. These items are easy to combine to make the robust and unique Life Signs. What makes difference between our proposed Life Signs for survivors' rescue and the existing Life Signs proposed by many researchers in the literature is that in our case there are not any instructions on the specific signs that the survivors waiting for rescue team should make before displaying it onto the visible place for the drone scanning over each area of the disaster to detect. The survivors have to decide by himself/herself what items to combine for the life signs by seeking around themselves what is available and not should have any similarity of shape with any sign anywhere. The sign should be unique with characteristic and shape proving that without human intervention these kinds of signs cannot exist. This will help the rescue team to move as quickly with not misdetection to save lives. This is the strong point of our application. We call it a "Only human made signs." Following shown in Fig. 1

Fig. 1 Example of items for the Life Signs

are the items we have chosen to test the Life Sign human survivor we developed.

- Kitchen knife
- Banana
- Forks
- Apple
- Orange
- Grape fruit
- Sweet potato
- Yellow tapes
- Cabbage
- Screw drivers
- Bottle of wine
- Bottle of alcohol
- Japanese white radish

Once the collection of these items is completed, we move on in combining them in any order, we want them to look like and to prove that these combinations are made only by human being and that they cannot be found anywhere. For the test of this application 6 signs have been made. After the combination of these signs are completed, we then took pictures of their pictures and process them with the developed system. The following are the output test.

A. Life Signs Sample

1. First Life Sign sample.

We drilled a banana and an orange with a screw driver from the top to the bottom, then just next to the banana we drilled an orange with a table fork obliquely. Fig.2 shows the combined life sign and the process image result. This kind of Life Sign cannot exist randomly. It shows that the only human who has the ability to do extraordinary things can make such combination.

(a) Original image (b) processing image
Fig.2 First life sign sample

Fig.2(a) is the original image and Fig.2(b) the processing image. It seems that the processing image does not look good in this article but when extend the picture, the contour of the orange, fork and the screw driver can be viewed.

2. Second Life Sign sample.

We pierce first a cabbage with a kitchen knife then pierce an apple with a screw driver, take the screw driver along with the drilled apple on it and add it into the cabbage and finally we drilled the cabbage with a Kitchen knife next to the apple with the screwdriver (Fig.3).

(a) Original image (b) processing image
Fig.3 Second life sign sample

Fig.3(a) represents the original image while Fig.3(b) the processing image. When looking at the processing image carefully it can be seen that the cabbage, apple and the Kitchen knife contour are clearly detected.

3. Third Life Sign sample.

For the third combination we drilled a banana and an orange with a screw driver from the top to the bottom, then just next to the banana we stab the orange again with a table fork. Next, the top of the screwdriver is attached to the bottle of wine with a yellow tape (Fig.4).

(a) Original image (b) processing image
Fig.4 third life sign sample

Fig.4 (b) is the processing result. All five items use for this sign can be view in keck eye and prove that the system is somehow good and promising.

4. Fourth Life Sign sample.

The fourth life sign combination uses one table spoon, fork, orange, apple, a cabbage and one screwdriver. Following is how this life sign has been made.

- We first pierced the orange straight with the table knife from down to the bottom
- Next, we pierced the orange with fork very close to the table Knife but obliquely.

- A screwdriver is used to drill an apple in the same way the orange and the table knife has been combined.
- Finally, a cabbage is put on a piece of wood as a support. Then we drilled the cabbage with the remaining of that table knife coming out of the orange from its bottom, so do the same as with the screwdriver in the apple (Fig5).

(a) original image (b) processing image
Fig.5 Fourth life sign sample

Fig.5 (a) shows the final life sign and Fig5(b) the processing image result. As can be seen in the processing image result, all items use in the life signs are clearly detect. This pays the way for the next step of the life sign recognition that will be to create an histogram of each item in the life sign.

5. Fifth Life Sign sample.

The fifth life sign is the combination of two different life signs as can be seen in the Fig.6.

(b) original image (b) processing image
Fig.6 Fifth life sign sample

For this sign we first took a Japanese white radish (Daikon) and a bottle of local alcohol, attached them together with a yellow tape. Next, we took the new made life sign put them together with previous sign on the piece of wood supporting the cabbage. Fig.6(a) shows the original image while Fig.6(b) the processing image result. As for the previous results, all the items are clearly detected even the label on the alcohol bottle seen be seen.

IV. DISCUSSION

This life sign image processing has been done in two different environments (1) in order to test the drawback or the weakness of the system and at the same time to see how these environments can affect or will affect the rescue system. (2) the results of the data collected from these environments will help us to make an adjustment on the system development. The life sign from Fig.2(a) to Fig.4(a) have been made inside the laboratory research facility (room) with light on. Theses original images are clear but the processing image results have some noises that prevent some signs contour to be seen correctly. On the other hand, life signs of Fig.5(a) and Fig.6(a) have been made outside the research laboratory during a sunny day. When compare the results obtained from Fig.2 to Fig.4 with the results of Fig.5 and Fig.6. We can see the big difference. The results of Fig.5 and Fig.6 more clearly than that of Fig.2 to Fig.4 and even a shadow can be viewed on Fig.6 (b). What we have learned from this experimental text is that, the environment is a great factor that plays an important role in the processing image result. We will from now on focus on removing the noise in order to make the contour be clearly view before any histogram can be made for the final recognition process.

V. CONCLUSION

This work proposes a Non-Predefined Life Signs Detection for Disaster Survivors Rescue. The Robert's gradient operator which consists of 2×2 matrix is used to compute the gradient of the image at every point in the image by evaluating the correlation of the image. The evaluation test has been made in two different environments which are. (1) inside the research laboratory room and (2) outside during a sunny day. The result has shown a big difference and that conclude that, the test environment plays an important role in the outcome of the processing image.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Niitsuma and K. Tokunaga. "Edge detection and Curvature Calculation in the Visual System." Proceedings of the 9th International Symposium of Artificial Life and Robotics, pp: ss-ss, Vol.1, 2004
- [2] D. Maar. "A Computational Investigation into the Human Representation and Processing of Visual Information. Information, W.H. Freeman, New York, 1982
- [3] D. Maar and E.Wil Dreth. "Theory of Edge

- Detection”. Proceedings of R.Soc. Lond. B. Vol.207, pp:187-217, 1980, Information, W.H. Freeman, New York, 1982
- [4] Satoru Odo, Kiyoshi Hoshino and Koji Yamada. Tracking and Recognition of Moving Object in a Monocular Image Sequence based on Visual Characteristics. Proceedings of the 9th International Symposium on Artificial Life and Robotics, pp: 79-82, Vol.1, 2004
- [5] Mutasem Khalil Aslmadi, Khairuddin Bin Omar Shahrul Azman Noah and Ibrahim Almarashdeh. “Fish recognition Based on Robust Features Extraction from Size and Shape Measurement Using Network. Journal of Computer Science Vol.6, Issue 10, 1008-1098, 2010
- [6] Zacharie Mbaitiga. “Security Guard Detecting Human Using Distribution Histogram Method “. Journal of Computer Science. Vol.6, Issue 10, pp:1144-1150, 2010
- [7] Surachai Panich. “Method of Object Detection for mobile Robot “. Journal of Computer Science. Vol.6, Issue 10, pp:1151-1153, 2010
- [8] John C. Russ. “The Image Processing Hard Book “. Fifth Edition. pp: 3-4, 2007
- [9] Tarek M. Mahmoud. “New Fast Skin Color of Science Engineering and Technology.” International Journal of Computer and Information Engineering. Vol.2, No.7, 2008.
- [10] William K.Pratt. Digital Image processing.” Third Edition. Pixel Soft Inco. USA, p: 443, 2001
- [11] Ruhuan Li, Dequiang Han, Jean Dezert and Yi Yang.” A Novel Edge Detection for Color Images Based on MCDM with Evidential Reasoning”. 20th International Conference on Information Fusion. China p: 768, 2017
- [12] J.M. Tacnet, J.Dezert. “Cautious OWA and Evidential Reasoning for Decision Making Under Uncertainty. Proceeding of the 14th International Conference on information Fusion. Chicago, Illinois, USA, July 5-8, 2011
- [13] D. Han, J. Dezert, J.M Tacnet, C. Han “A Fuzzy Cautious OWA Approach with Evidential Reasoning. International Conference on information Fusion. July 9-12, 2012